

Network of Framing Disease: Qualitative Review

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Background and aims: Opportunity exists to extrapolate iconography to framing disease by qualitative review. An icon is framed in four phases: 1. pre-iconographical description, 2. iconographical description, 3. iconographical interpretation, 4. iconological interpretation.¹ However, disease is framed in two phases: 1. biological, 2. social.² The International Classification of Diseases (ICD) looks most like ICONCLASS for art.

Methods: Qualitative review by one reviewer by annotating iconography in Brumberg's essay³ on anorexia nervosa in the book Framing Disease².

Results: Iconography could be extrapolated to framing disease. Some examples were: food refusal, compulsive activity and value slimness (phase 1), anorexia nervosa (phase 2), individual - or group reaction (phase 3), no private toilet with a flush in Victorian time so no mix of anorexia nervosa with bulimia (phase 4), fitness and exercise cult in 1970 so increase of compulsive running (phase 4).

Conclusions: The result continues the trend of framing disease. It might be a practical organizer of study material for medical students. An operating rule of Lockheed's Skunk Works, a business that builds technologically advanced airplanes, is to push more basic inspection back to subcontractors and vendors to avoid duplication.⁴ Maybe this means that there is a crossover between phase three and - one. Van Straten warns that the boundaries between the individual phases are often superfluous.¹

References

1. Van Straten, R. (1994). An Introduction to Iconography. Taylor & Francis.
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3. Brumberg, J.J. (1992). The Case of Anorexia Nervosa. Essay in Framing Disease (Rosenberg and Golden, 1922).
4. Rich, B.R., Janos, L. (1994). Skunk Works. Little, Brown and Company.